

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
 THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
 COMMUNITIES
 NO 732559

Dissemination, Communication and community Engagement Plan-v1

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable presents the initial Dissemination Plan for the ToyLabs project, it gives the guidelines and expected participation of partners regarding dissemination and communication activities. This document will be kept updated in order to include new opportunities in dissemination.

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

WP	Work Package
DISS	Dissemination
OBJ	Objective
TSIG	ToyLabs Special Interest Group
DoW	Document of Work

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable is released within the context of Work Package 6 "Dissemination, Communication and Community Building". WP6 aims at addressing the strategic objective of extending the ToyLabs offerings towards key players like toy industry SMEs, FabLabs, Toy Safety experts, child-life specialists etc. and at diffusing the scientific and technological related knowledge acquired through the project.

In particular, the WP6 purposes are:

- To widely disseminate the project concept, developments and findings to various stakeholder segments: Scientific Community; Industry; SMEs, FabLabs and Web Entrepreneurs in an interactive way;
- To open up the specifications and the design of the methodology, as well as the piloting and evaluation phases of the pilots, to allow any interested innovator to contribute to the development of the ToyLabs methodology;
- To raise awareness, communicate and diffuse the knowledge acquired during the ToyLabs implementation in scientific, industrial and standardisation communities;
- To outline a feasible and effective community building strategy, customised to the target groups' characteristics and accompanied by appropriate means of engagement. Such a strategy will be also extended towards planning the necessary dissemination and communication activities;
- To carry out a concrete set of activities that will ensure the success of the dissemination, communication and community building strategies;
- To develop an interactive and user-friendly web site to inform the general public and relevant stakeholders about ToyLabs and have a successful social media strategy that will provide the maximum visibility and public awareness of ToyLabs;
- To publish results in international conferences and workshops in order to inform the various researchers about the ToyLabs goals and achievements and to gather valuable information on related issues;
- To diffuse the dissemination and training material to be produced in collaboration with all work packages;
- To actively participate in European Commission's instruments and cultivate concentration activities with the on-going creative industry's projects.

The present document is the first Deliverable in WP5, presenting the initial dissemination plan of the project. Its purpose is to outline a dissemination plan for the realisation of the objectives of WP6 explained above.

1.1 TARGET AUDIENCES

It is important to identify the potential targeted audiences of ToyLabs along with the specific interest they may have in the project. An initial list of these target groups for ToyLabs is detailed in the following table.

Target Group	Description	Interest in the Project
A - Manufacturing Toy Industry SMEs	Individuals, teams and enterprises of various scales that are part of the ToyLabs value chain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilisation of project's results in everyday operations • Enhance industrial innovation by blending with in- house artefacts • Training on project's outcomes • Participation in the project's events
B - FabLabs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilisation of project's results in everyday operations • Opportunity to enter the toy industry
C - Toy Safety Experts		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to establish their name in the toy industry • Exploitation of new market opportunities • Participation in the project's events
D - Childhood professionals and Parent Associations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilisation of project's results with appropriate incentives • Participation in the project's events
E – IT Industry Players		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in project's events • Exploitation of project's open source results • Inspiration for new ideas and applications

F – Industry Associations & Technology Clusters	European initiatives and clusters (like FIWARE and BDVA), research communities, associations, federations (like IMS, EFFRA, IFIP, IEEE, NEM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers...) • Dissemination of project's results to their members • Bilateral participation in events for knowledge exchange
G – Creative Industries Projects' Stakeholders	Participants, project partners and relevant stakeholders active in the H2020 projects related to Creative Industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of common topics • Synergies and collaborations for results promotion • Enhancing innovation through results combination • Co-organisation of events
H - Researchers and Academia	Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further advance the project's research • Extension / reuse of the project's innovative technologies to other application domains • Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project's concept and results • Participation in the project's events
I - Policy Makers & Standardization Organizations	Policy-makers at any level like EC Directorates and Units, Ministries and Governments, Regulatory Agencies, Standardisation Organisations (CEN, ISO, ETSI, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the project's Social-Technological- Economic- Environmental-Political (STEEP) aspects • Definition of future research and innovation directions based on project's acquired knowledge • Inputs for standardisation activities
J – General Public (Consumers as End Users)	Civil society representatives, general public and anyone interested in the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the benefits offered by the proposal • Take part in the activities of the project

Table 1 Target Audiences for Dissemination & Communication

2. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The dissemination strategy aims to widely diffuse the project advancements to the different targeted audiences with appropriate mechanisms in a timely manner as well as that the key stakeholders for the project's exploitation and market update are early engaged and actively participating to the various project's implementation phases. Dissemination is instrumental to effectively promote the exploitation activities, while it is closely related to the communication activities (defined in Section 3).

The main objective is to implement an intensive, yet clear, strategy and conduct effective dissemination, communication and exploitation activities from the very early stages of the project's implementation. All partners are committed throughout the project to mobilize the appropriate stakeholders in order to multiply the effects of dissemination and exploitation activities.

2.1 OBJECTIVES AND DISSEMINATION APPROACH

The dissemination activities will deal with the diffusion of scientific and technological knowledge generated within the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact by informing the European target audiences A-J, as identified in Table 1. The dissemination strategy to be applied in the project is aligned to the following objectives:

- DISS. OBJ. I: To ensure maximum visibility of the project in the target audiences via appropriate key messages. (Target Audiences: A-I)
- DISS. OBJ. II: To timely diffuse the scientific and technological knowledge generated in the project within and beyond the project's consortium. (Target Audiences: A-I)
- DISS. OBJ. III: To establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer. (Target Audiences: F-G)
- DISS. OBJ. IV: To engage the targeted audiences to get feedback and validate the project's results. (Target Audiences: A, B, C, E, G, H, I)
- DISS. OBJ. V: To attract potential users / clients and stimulate the appropriate market segments to support the project's exploitation strategy. (Target Audiences: A, B, C, D, E, H)
- DISS. OBJ. VI: To encourage the development of further outcomes in new initiatives. (Target Audiences: A, B, E, F, H)

Dissemination activities will be collectively performed by all partners, according to each partner's profile and expertise. Meaning, the industrial partners will

approach relevant industry-sectors, as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners will focus on disseminating the project results towards research institutes and universities across Europe. Individual dissemination intentions per partner are placed in Section 7.

2.2 DISSEMINATION PLAN

The initial dissemination plan aims to ensure that the suitable dissemination activity is chosen depending on the target audience and its intensity is regulated according to the phase of the project where it is implemented.

The duration of the project has been chronologically divided in three phases that comprise different objectives. The different dissemination activities are more specified for each phase. In Phase I the main objective is to raise awareness, activities' intensity in this phase will be low. Phase II is centred in inform and interact with audiences and Phase III will focus in promoting the project, this two phases require high intensity. There is planned a final Phase IV related to Post-Project Dissemination to guarantee further promotion and exploitation of project results beyond the implementation.

The dissemination plan has to be evaluated and updated at the end of each phase. It can and should be modified to include any new opportunity that could benefit to the project dissemination.

The figure below shows the different Dissemination Mechanisms and the Phases in which the project has been divided to plan the dissemination. The content of the different columns shows the specific activities to be performed in each phase.

Dissemination Mechanisms	BigDataOcean Phases	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M6)	Phase II: Inform and Interact (M7-M12)	Phase III: Promote (M13-M18)
		Diss. Obj. I, III Activities' Intensity: Low Target Audiences: ALL	Diss. Obj. I, II, III, IV Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL	Diss. Obj. II, III, IV, V, VI Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL
(D1) Organisation of Project Events		D1.I) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences	D1.II) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences, industry events & fairs; Organisation of hackathon	D1.III) Organisation of workshops in industry events; Organisation of hackathon & demo events
(D2) Participation to Conferences & Workshops		D2.I) Participation to events; Presentation of project scope; Interaction with participants	D2.II) Presentation of project's results to events; Representation in booths	D2.III) Presentation of project's results and business case to events; Representation in demo sessions
(D3) Scientific Publications		D3.I) Publication of position papers / review papers in conferences	D3.II) Publication of methodology papers in conferences	D3.III) Publication of overall project's results in journals & industry magazines
(D4) Community Building / Engagement with Stakeholders		D4.I) Establishment of contact points; Liaison with industry communities and networks; Promotion of project's communication material; Interviews	D4.II) Validation of results with key stakeholders in events / online; Interaction with industry communities and networks; Invitation to project's events	D4.III) Creation of network of potential users; Promotion of project's application stories; Invitation for demos; Training webinars
(D5) Collaboration and synergies with projects		D5.I) Synergies identification; Establishment of contact points; Exchange of ideas & intentions	D5.II) Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, Joint presence in events	D5.III) Joint engagement in events / demo days
(D6) Internal Dissemination in partner's networks		D6.I) Project's links & news in partners' website, social media accounts, newsletters	D6.II) Inclusion of projects' results in partners' events	D6.III) Demonstration of results in partners' premises; Training; Reuse of results

Figure 1 ToyLabs Dissemination Plan

2.3 EXPECTED IMPACT OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

In order to evaluate the project's dissemination impact there have been established a set of specific metrics per each dissemination activity. The effectiveness of dissemination will be assessed during the life of the project and the results obtained will be presented in each reporting period.

Activity	Expected Impact	Related KPIs	Targets
D1	Increased collaboration with other relevant initiatives; Synergies establishment for joint research, information exchange and dissemination; increased awareness.	Number of workshops organized	2
		Number of demo events	2
D2	Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives; information about latest technologies / advancements; liaisons with other initiatives; Increased awareness.	Number of attended events	10
		Number of events with project's presentation	7
		Number of project's demo booths	1
D3	Validation of project's concept, findings and advancements; Promotion of results to scientific communities; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange	Number of conference papers	5
		Number of journal papers	2
		Number of articles in industry magazines	6

	with relevant communities and initiatives.		
D4	Communication of project news, events & results; Validation of project's concept, findings and advancements; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; Attraction of potential clients and adopters; increased awareness.	Number of FabLabs contacted	20
		Number of Toy Safety Experts contacted	10
		Number of childhood professionals and parent associations informed about the project	20
		Number of webinars	2
D5	Knowledge exchange; Mutual validation of results; Joint dissemination activities; Attraction of potential partners for research collaborations .	Number of projects with synergies	10
		Number of joint activities	3
D6	Communication of project news, events & results; Validation of project's concept, findings and advancements; Ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; increased awareness.	Number of internal partners' events	4
		Number of links to the project's website	7
		Number of training sessions	2

Table 2 Dissemination Activities Impact

3. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

3.1 OBJECTIVES AND COMMUNICATION APPROACH

Communication activities include all actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders. In this way the aim is to maximise the project's contribution to innovation and attract a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace and benefit from the project's advancements. In this direction, the project will:

- Define concrete and measurable objectives for the communication activities linked with the appropriate target groups.
- Implement a solid, modern and inclusive communication strategy, accompanied by a realistic plan to reach these objectives.
- Set up the different channels, tools and mechanisms that will be used to implement the communication plan and reach the targeted audiences.
- Define the guidelines for the implementation of communication and dissemination actions.
- Closely monitor the impact of the communication in order to be able to apply corrective actions whenever necessary and identify opportunities that can maximize visibility.

The communication strategy is driven by the following communication objectives which are directly linked with the different phases of the project and the targeted audience:

- COMM.OBJ. I: To create awareness of the project among the full range of potential adopters / users in the general public. (Target Audiences: A-J)
- COMM.OBJ. II: To provide a clear view of the project's concept, goals and results by formulating adapted key messages, and preparing communication material. (Target Audiences: A-J)
- COMM.OBJ. III: To create an active community of potential users and collect feedback to be taken into account by the project's activities. (Target Audiences: A-J)
- COMM.OBJ. IV: To prepare the ground for the exploitation of project's results. (Target Audiences: A-J)
- COMM.OBJ. V: To support targeted dissemination of the project's results. (Target Audiences: A-J)
- COMM.OBJ. VI: To foster the wide adoption of the project's results in industry and society. (Target Audiences: J)

3.2 COMMUNICATION PLAN

is important to effectively address the communication objectives and meet the expectations of the target audience groups, for this purpose it is important to pay specific attention to adapt the communication means, the measures and the content both to the needs and knowledge level of each target group as well as the stage of the project and specific needs that may appear.

Like the dissemination plan, the initial communication plan aims to ensure that the suitable dissemination activity is chosen depending on the target audience and for each phase of the project.

The duration of the project has been chronologically divided in three phases that comprise different objectives. The different communication activities are more specified for each phase. In Phase I the main objective is to raise awareness, Phase II is centred in diffusing knowledge and Phase III will focus in communication culmination. There is planned a final Phase IV related to Post-Project Dissemination to guarantee further promotion and exploitation of project results beyond the implementation.

The dissemination plan has to be evaluated and updated at the end of each phase. It can and should be modified to include any new opportunity that could benefit to the project dissemination.

The figure below shows the different Communication Mechanisms and the Phases in which the project has been divided to plan the communication. The content of the different columns shows the specific activities to be performed in each phase.

Communication Mechanisms	BigDataOcean Phases	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M6)	Phase II: Diffuse Knowledge (M7-M12)	Phase III: Communication Culmination (M13-M18)
		<i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	<i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	<i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, IV, V, VI</i>
(C1) ToyLabs Website		C1.I) Design & Development of an intuitive and responsive project’s web site; Search engine optimization	C1.II) Regular update of the website content; Watch website’s analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest	C1.III) Regular update of the website content; Clear visibility of results, demo / application material in an interactive way
(C2) ToyLabs Social Media Presence		C2.I) Establishment of presence in: Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags; Upload public material; Follow influencers of the domain; Engage with other projects and initiatives	C2.II) Promote project’s outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags	C2.III) Promote project’s outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content (more sporadically)
(C3) ToyLabs Blog		C3.I) Deploy project’s blog; Provide blog posts related to project’s positioning & technologies	C3.II) Provide frequent blog posts to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback	C3.III) Publish frequent blog posts to demonstrate and promote project’s results
(C4) Traditional Media		C4.I) Press release to announce the project’s launch	C4.II) Press releases to announce the significant events / results	C4.III) Press releases to promote the business case of the project’s results
(C5) Communication Material		C5.I) Design logo and project identity; Prepare project factsheet, brochure, banner, e-Newsletter and promo video	C5.II) Prepare revised brochure, banner and frequent releases of e-Newsletter; Publish blogs / news in EU instruments (e.g. Cordis News, research*eu magazines etc.)	C5.III) Prepare final brochure, banner, frequent releases of e-Newsletter and video demonstrators; Publish blogs / news in EU dissemination instruments

Figure 2 ToyLabs Communication Plan

In order for the communication strategy to achieve its listed objectives, all partners commit to undertake the necessary activities. The communication strategy of the project will assign responsibilities to partners according to their domain of expertise and existing liaisons in order to achieve the optimum results in terms of communication.

Another important aspect of the communication strategy is that specific attention should be paid to adapt the measures and the content to the needs and knowledge levels of these groups in order to meet the different objectives and satisfy the expectations of the target audience groups. This will be facilitated mainly through the employment of a vast number of communication means, which can be used (and tailored to) different stakeholder groups, while the information that will be pushed to these groups will vary depending on current status/progress and needs of the project.

Furthermore, it has to be noted that the creation of a community of interested stakeholders and potential users will ensure the transfer of data and knowledge beyond the project duration, ensuring in such a way the continuation of research

and the increased take-up of results. All partners should take part in building this community.

3.3 EXPECTED IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In order to evaluate the project's communication impact there have been established a set of specific metrics per each communication activity. The effectiveness of communication will be assessed during the life of the project and the results obtained will be presented in each reporting period.

Activity	Expected Impact	Related KPIs	Targets
C1	Main online information point; Communication of project news, events & results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links; increased awareness.	Number of unique visitors	3.000
		Average duration of visits	2 min
		Number of page views	6.000
C2	Increasing visibility to stakeholders active in social media; Attainment of interest of stakeholders; Viral marketing by "word of mouth" through the followers; Direct communication mechanism with followers.	Number of accumulative followers	450
		Number of accumulative posts	750
		Number of interactions	200
C3	Communication of main project's concepts and advancements in a catchy and easily understandable manner.	Number of posts	20
		Number of interactions	50
C4	Communication of project news, events & results; increased awareness.	Number of press releases	4
C5	Unique branding and visual identity of the project; Provision of instant information about the project; Creating a unified experience for the audiences targeted; improved communication of results and information provision during events.	Number of project's factsheets 1 brochures and banners	5
		Number of newsletters	4
		Number of videos	3
		Number of blog posts in EC mechanisms	3

Table 3 Communication Activities Impact

4. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT PLAN

ToyLabs gives great attention on establishing an active community of prospective users to engage them with the project's platform from project's early steps. It is crucial to broaden the community both during the project's duration but also after its end, as well as to create "loyal", active users that will consistently participate and provide their feedback. Satisfied users are more likely to talk about ToyLabs to other users too, thus helping to further widen the community.

T6.3 from ToyLabs Work Plan exclusively deals with community building, showcasing its upgraded importance for the project. Four stakeholder types represent ToyLabs community and is necessary to be reached and engaged: FabLabs, Toy Safety Experts, Childhood Professionals and Parents' Associations.

A Community Engagement Plan is presented along the following lines, divided in different phases, along with a description of the approach to be used in each of them.

Phase I: Early project's phase (M1 – M3)

During this early phase, the consortium will form the initial community that will form the ToyLabs special interest group (TSIG). The TSIG will help run the pilots and get early feedback. For this purpose, four open calls will be announced, one per country. Each call will choose at least three individuals with diverse characteristics: one child psychologist, one childhood professional and one parent (or parent association).

TSIG will be responsible for participating in each pilot execution providing their feedback on submitted designs as well as supporting communication of project concept and results to their network contacts.

For the community of Toy Security experts needed to run the pilot's use cases, AIJU's network will be exploited as they can guarantee a sufficient number of Toy Security experts willing to participate in the project.

Phase II: Middle and Late Project's phase (M4 – M18)

After the formation of TIG, the pilots can run effectively producing credible results. However, it is essential to create a sustainable community of users/experts during the 'project to ensure successful exploitation of project's results after the end of the project. To this end dissemination and communication activities are identified in sections 2 and 3. However, specific focus for community building will be given on the following activities.

- **TSIG's network of contacts:** TSIG's network of contacts as a starting point for expanding ToyLabs community.
- **Social Media Viral Marketing Activities:**
 - Twitter bot for ToyLabs needs targeting well known toy influencers and mentioning specific hashtags to promote the project and drive traffic to the website. In order to identification influencers the consortium will use ToyLabs Social Analytics Engine and will exploit already known toy fan groups provided by the pilots.
 - YouTube: At least two videos promoting ToyLabs results promoted by all project partners to succeed many views
 - All social media accounts: It is of high importance to keep an active presence in all social media. All partners should send material susceptible to be published. AIJU and NTUA will evaluate this content and publish periodically.
- **Reference or interview on well-known tech and toy blogs:** for this part at least 3 references and 1 interview are necessary
- **Participation in toy events and trade shows with a Demo:** Attending to events could significantly boost community building since they are targeted to both professionals and interested general public. Anyone attending to this events are usually genuinely interested in the toy industry (as general public for example parents and teachers). Consequently, such events may conform a great way to engage new users. Gifts to the trade fair participants from the pilots will be prepared to incentivise the participation.
 - All partners should provide a potential list of events attendance which may be interesting for the project. For this purpose, a specific section in Afresco (document repository used in the project) has been prepared.
- **Presence in Additive Manufacturing Platform and FoFAM project Roadmap.** It is very important to include ToyLabs in this platforms in order to disseminate in specialised sites and have more presence among interested public
- Participation in other well-known events, not necessarily related to the toy industry in order to get exposure in the start-up community and get press coverage.
- **Email marketing:** Email summaries will be sent to the users with

successful and trending projects to increase involvement. Anyone interested in the project will be offered to join a mailing list to provide them with further information. This database will remain confidential and the personal data will not be used for purposes beyond the project.

Phase III: After the end of the project

After the end of the project, a sustainable community of users will have been created. However, social media presence should continue to be intense, along with other activities of the previous phase, such as email marketing to reserve and further widen ToyLabs community. Phase III specific plan will be set according to the insights gained from previous phases.

5. MEANS OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

5.1 DISSEMINATION MECHANISMS

5.1.1 ORGANISATION OF PROJECT EVENTS

ToyLabs will organise two international workshops and two demo events, Figure 1 explains how they should be organised depending the phase of the project we are in to realise different objectives. Organising events pretends to increase the awareness of the project and increase collaboration with other relevant initiatives, also establish synergies for joint research and exchange information and disseminate the project.

Workshops will be organised in scientific conferences, industry events and fairs depending on the phase of the project. IT is important to find the right place in order to disseminate the project to the right audiences.

The workshops and demo events will provide in-depth information and materials to the attendees in order to explain the functioning of the project and platform.

For all events it is important to keep record of the feedback obtained, participants, and any relevant information.

5.1.2 PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS

While attending to different events partner will take on presentations regarding the project scope, results and business case. It is important to interact with the different target groups that might have an interest in the project providing them with information about the potential impact of the ToyLabs platform. It is important to choose the right events taking into account that people attending these events have a pre-existing interest in the sector.

In the DoW there is included a non-exhaustive list of candidate academic conferences and industrial events: International Conference on Advanced Collaborative Networks, Systems and Applications (COLLA 2016), International Conference on Communication Software and Networks (ICCSN-IEEE 2016), International Conference on Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality and Computer Graphics (SALENTO AVR 2016), International Conference on Communications, Computation, Networks and Technologies (INNOV 2016)

Besides, in Alfresco there has been created a list where all partners should include the different events with interest to the project. When attending to these events partners should make a presentation or bring dissemination material.

During the project the consortium should attend to at least 10 events 7 of which should include a project presentation and one demo booth.

For all events it is important to keep record of the feedback obtained, participants, and any relevant information.

5.1.3 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Academic and scientific publications, press releases, articles and announcements will help ToyLabs to further disseminate different aspects of the project as well as reach wider audience. In figure 1 the publications are detailed depending on the phase of the project. Publication of position papers and review papers in conferences, methodology papers in conferences and publication of overall project's results in journals and industry magazines. Important deliverables as methodology might as well be published to provide insights of the project to different interested parties.

In the DoW there is included a non-exhaustive list of candidate journals, this: International Journal of Managing Information Technology (IJMIT 2016), International Journal of Next - Generation Network (IJNGN 2016), International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT 2016), International Journal of

Computational Science, Information Technology and Control Engineering (IJSITCE 2016). All partners should propose other interesting choices where publishing could be useful.

5.1.4 INTERNAL DISSEMINATION IN PARTNERS' NETWORK

All partners should disseminate the project in their own network by sharing links and news in their own website, social media accounts, newsletter, etc. Also partners should include the project in the events they organize if possible and prepare demonstrations of the results.

5.2 COMMUNICATION MECHANISMS

There are different mechanisms to ensure a proper communication of the project depending on the stage, objective and audience target.

5.2.1 TOYLABS WEBSITE

The ToyLabs website will be the main focal point of the project it will present relevant information related to objectives, members, public deliverables, publications, etc.

There will be a contact section where anyone interested in the project can contact the consortium and get more information.

The project structure will be the following:

- ToyLabs Platform
- Project Info
 - Introduction
 - Objectives/Goal
 - Work Structure
 - Consortium
- Resources
 - Publications (academic and press)
 - Deliverables
- News (articles and blog)
- Contact us

Some sections may vary during the project depending the needs of the project.

Site statistics will be tracked by Google Analytics to get a proper view of the traffic and interest generated by the website.

5.2.2 TOYLABS SOCIAL MEDIA

There have been created various accounts in different social media channels. It is important to use a different channel depending on the character of the dissemination material, the objectives and the specific target audience group it is directed to.

Actions to be taking in social media are: reproduce relevant content, monitor hashtags, upload public material, engage other projects, promote project outcomes and events, interact with followers.

All partners should provide two potential posts per week, AIJU and NTUA will evaluate the information and publish it in the corresponding site.

The tools to be used are the following:

- LinkedIn ToyLabs Group

The LinkedIn group will be used as the main discussion and validation mechanism with experts and other interested parties

- Twitter ToyLabs account

The Twitter account will be used as a dissemination tool to share news, events and other announcements to enlarge the ToyLabs community.

Horizon 2020 has an official twitter account @EU_H2020 to create a community of projects, they are also using the hashtag #ReachImpactEU

When sharing breaking news that show the impact of the project it is important to use this hashtag and tag @EU_H2020

Figure 3 ToyLabs Twitter page

- Facebook ToyLabs Fan page

Facebook is a great tool to engage larger audiences. The Facebook fan page aims to reach out and engage stakeholders and enlarge the audiences and engage them. For special posts (events, important news, etc.) it is advisable to boost publications in order to reach more public.

Figure 4 ToyLabs Facebook Page

- Slide share ToyLabs account

This platform will serve as a way to share different presentations related to the project with the objective of maximise awareness of project's presentations

- YouTube ToyLabs Channel

The YouTube channel will be used to share different videos: events, promotional videos, etc.

Figure 5 ToyLabs YouTube channel

- Research Gate ToyLabs account

The Research Gate account will be used as a meeting place to finalize details, collaborate and communicate. It will be used to upload research output including papers, data, methods, presentations, etc. Users may also follow the activities of other users and engage in discussions with them.

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Figure 6 Research Gate ToyLabs account

- Paper.li ToyLabs account

Paper.li creates an on-line newspaper to collect and disseminate original ToyLabs content and relevant items, posts articles, etc.

Figure 7 ToyLabs Paper.li account

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732559.

5.2.3 TOYLABS BLOG

ToyLabs' blog will be included in the website, it will contain blog posts related to project's positioning and technologies. It is important to provide frequent blog posts to generate discussion and receive feedback on specific issues important to the project. In the last stage the posts will focus on the project result and demonstrations.

5.2.4 TRADITIONAL MEDIA

Traditional media such as scientific magazines, newspapers and journals will be used to release important milestones in the project, results and events also important deliverables could be published in a more attractive way. It is important to reach interested audiences and this kind of media reach this objective.

5.2.5 COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

- Project Logo

The project logo was designed in the early stages of the project, since then it has been used in all the documents, publications, presentations, etc. The logo is available in Alfresco in a vector graphic file format so it can be adapted to different sizes and resolutions.

Figure 8 ToyLabs Logo

- Factsheet

A factsheet has to be developed, it has to include the most important points regarding the project. All partners should distribute it printed and electronic format (it will be available in the ToyLabs website). The objective is to give a general and complete idea about the ToyLabs project.

- Brochure

The brochure will include the scope of the project including technical details, pilots, information about the consortium and contact details. It will be distributed by partners at relevant events as well as in their own network. It will be also available in the project's website

- E-Newsletter

The newsletter will be produced to keep the audience informed on any updates, major achievements, tasks, events, etc. Anyone interested in the project will be offered to join a mailing list to receive this information. The newsletter has to offer the information on how they can get in touch with the project. All partners should distribute it between their own contacts and it will be present in the project's website.

- Promotional video

A promotional video will be created to promote the project in a more dynamic way. It will contain basic information and the project contact. It will be uploaded to different social media and website. All partners should share it in their own networking contact.

- Promotional Material

It is planned to produce different promotional material that could work as gifts to events attendants interested in the project, they also have to show some insights of the project. Toy manufacturers could work on personalised toys and FabLabs could have some 3D printed designs that include the logo (e.g. phone case) All partners should give ideas on which things might be interesting.

6. GUIDELINES

In order to ensure a firm dissemination plan there has been established a series of rules, policies and organisational guidelines for this issue. In the next sections the partners responsibilities and the methodology of the dissemination activities will be defined.

6.1 RESPONSABILITIES

The responsibilities in dissemination activities have been distributed between the Work Package Leader and all partners that have effort in this WP.

- The responsibility of ensure an effective, timely and appropriate dissemination and communication of the project concept, progress and accomplishments lands on the WP5 Leader AIJU
- All partner should work to ensure maximum visibility of the project achievements by promoting and spreading the dissemination and communication material
- All partners should suggest potential opportunities to maximise the dissemination. The project dissemination plan will be constantly updated to implement any opportunity that might help the project dissemination.
- All partners should declare their intention to participate or organise an event as well as inform the WP Leader on the outcomes. In Alfresco there is a list ready to fill where all partners should include potential assisting to events.
- All partners should contribute to build the project's user community and distribute announcements and press releases in their own individual networks in different countries.
- All partners should contribute in building the project's community by organising workshops and demo events.
- Regarding social media, all partners should promote the project page through their own accounts and provide material for dissemination.

6.2 RULES FOR PUBLICATIONS

All communication and dissemination activities shall follow the procedures agreed in ToyLabs Consortium Agreement.

For any planned publication, notice shall be given to all partners 15 days prior the date of submission, any objections to the planned publication will be communicated not later than 7 days before submission.

All publications shall follow the next guidelines:

- All publications and presentations should follow EU rules for publication
- Partners must clearly acknowledge the EC's contribution in all publication and explicitly mention the project's name alongside with the grant agreement No
- All publications should respect the consortium agreement
- All presentations should be constructed following the available templates
- Presentations or publications should not include classified or non-public material
- All publications should be available to all the partners prior to the date of submission and can be reused or modified.

6.3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES PLANING AND REPORTING

Related to planning, in alfresco there is available a spreadsheet of possible events where it might be interesting to attend in order to disseminate the project. All partners should fill- in information in this regard. This way WP leader will keep track of the relevant activities. This list of events might be updated during the project.

In order to report after any event, there is a template available in Alfresco (repository of project's document). This document records information regarding size of audience, feedback received, outcomes and discussions, suggestions, etc. Partners involved in any dissemination activity should fill this template as soon as possible after the completion of the activity. Timely and efficient reporting shall benefit the compilation of dissemination activities report.

7. INDIVIDUAL DISSEMINATION PLAN

The following tables show the individual dissemination plan presented in the application form, this information is open to modification in the next versions of the dissemination plan as new opportunities appear.

AIJU	
Description	<p>AIJU envisage promoting project results by means of scientific journals and professional magazines. These activities be carried out not only within the project time line but also after its completion. Publication activities will be related to ToyLabs but predominantly carried out on behalf of respective researchers. This dissemination will be focused on the generation of presentations and publications in scientific conferences or journals and specialised magazines.</p> <p>As we are at the beginning of the project, AIJU will be actively analysing the different alternatives in order to find those publications more appropriate to disseminate the results regarding scientific dissemination activities. Other opportunities could come up during the project timeline.</p> <p>In general, all dissemination efforts of the project will be directed to these objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of project results in different occasions such as workshops, international fairs or events promoted by European Commission. • Uploading not only relevant content for general public and specific for people interested regarding the project but also a repository for the project partners in order to share and exchange information. • General purpose promotion of the project (activities, advertising material, newsletters, etc.) using media channels. <p>The main dissemination activities carried out by AIJU will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press releases during the project. • Article of presentation of the results of the project on the Magazine of AIJU each 3-4 months • Dissemination and promotion of results at scientific and business events • Demonstrations to potential customers.
Target audiences	TOY's SME's, industry experts, Researchers
Expected impact of activities	<p>We have other kind of quantitative indicators, associated to the Project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Brochure distributed: 1500 • 4 Press Releases/Articles in AIJU's magazine • 2 Toy Fair Participation (European level) • 2 seminars organized by AIJU: more than 50 participants from Toys Companies
Indicative list of events, academic conferences, industry fairs	International Toy Fair 2017 (February) Nuremberg (Germany)
Liaisons/Participation to standardisation Committees	AIJU is an active member of the Committees that set the standards for child products' (toys CEN/TC 52, childcare articles CEN/TC 252, playgrounds CEN/TC136/SC1, electrical toys

	<p>CENELEC/TC61 WG7 and other consumer articles). TOYLAB including via the websites of other projects and initiatives where AIJU is member:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sectorial Platforms as EFFRA - European Factory of the Future Research • Association, PLATECMA –Technological Platform of Traditional • Manufacturing Sectors (SMT), Manufacture, Eumat – European Technology • Platform for Advanced Engineering Materials and Technologies design, etc. • Federations & Associations: ESBA (European Small Commerce Association, • EMOTA – the European e-Commerce and distance selling, Business Europe, • FEDMA – Federation of European Direct Marketing Association, e- Commerce Europe, IAB Europe, Eurochambres, Toy Industries of Europe, the British toy business and a large etcetera.
<p>Liaisons/Participation to related Industry Communities/Associations</p>	<p>Internationally, one can name different platforms and leisure associations, which, AIJU participates actively:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDEAN: European Design for All Network accessibility • IPA: International Play Association • ITRA: International Toy Research Association • ASTRA: American Specialty Toy Retailing Association • TIA: Toy Industry Association (U.S.) • TIE: Toy Industries of Europe. • Design for all Foundation

Table 4 AIJU individual dissemination plan

SINGULAR LOGIC	
<p>Description</p>	<p>Singular Logic maintains a large network of both commercial and R&D business partners, to whom plans to communicate Toylabs in accordance to the planned dissemination strategy of the project. In addition to that, SLG targets at specific dissemination activities in order to further disseminate the project, which include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation in industry-oriented conferences which are addressed (among others) to managers and key decision makers from private and public sector providing a significant networking opportunity with the IT industry, including developers, integrators and consultants. The company (and the European projects department in particular), which participates regularly in such conferences - in many of them with invited talks - plans to present and promote this way the outcomes of Toylabs, especially at the period close to the end of the project that the Toylabs platform and tools will be ready and pretty mature.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Articles about Toylabs will be published in the corporate magazine reaching 450 professionals and business executives. Selected articles will be also sent to the huge business network of the company in Southeastern Europe. - Joint dissemination with relevant running projects like the MSCA-EID-SENECA project which finishes at the end of 2018. In collaboration with this project, as well as with other research activities under implementation, SLG will investigate possibilities for joint publications concerning the project results in relevant conferences (e.g., IEEE Cloud, IEEE Cloud Computing and other) and we will target joint activities for public outreach (e.g. participation at European Researchers' Night). Furthermore, SLG will disseminate the project results (via newsletters and potentially invited talks to meetings) to its R&D partner network in the area of software engineering, cloud and IT security (from running and past relevant projects) with a view to investigate potential exploitation opportunities of the project results. - Organization of events targeting in particular business partners and customers (in possible collaboration with other projects to maximize the impact of the events). At least two events demonstrating the project results to key decision makers in the company, business partners and customers will take place.
Target audiences	SMEs, industry experts, Researchers, general public
Expected impact of activities	Referring to the individual dissemination activities of SLG in Toylabs, the following targets are set as minimum: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 Press Releases/Articles in corporate magazine (450 professionals) • 2 Industrial Fair participation (national level) • 2 publications in relevant conferences (international level) • Participation in one researchers' night in collaboration with running Marie- Curie project SENECA • 2 events organized by the company (target audience: key decision makers in the company, business partners and customers; More than 20 participants from distinct companies)
Indicative list of events, academic conferences, industry fairs	CLOUD-IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing, IEE CloudCom- IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing Technology and Science (mainly industrial tracks)
Liaisons/Participation to related Industry Communities/Associations	Singular Logic belongs to the Association of IT and Communications Greek Enterprises (SEPE) and it maintains a large network of both commercial and R&D business partners.

Table 5 SINGULAR LOGIC individual dissemination plan

NTUA	
Description	Dissemination of scientific results and practical examples through highly ranked conferences and journals is envisaged, exploiting the extensive experience of NTUA in publishing innovative scientific work. NTUA will also communicate the knowledge, advances and innovation potential to the different communities and networks it consists part of. NTUA commits itself to participate in workshops and/or international conferences in order to come in direct contact with other academic institutions, enterprises, researchers and other projects’ stakeholders and exchange current practices and opinions. Finally, leveraging its experience on Social Networks, NTUA will diffuse information around ToyLabs on various Web 2.0 channels supporting the global visibility of the project.
Target audiences	Academia, Researchers, Standardisation bodies, Public Administrations and Policy Officers
Indicative list of events, academic conferences, industry fairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE International Conference on Big Data Science and Engineering (BigDataSE) • International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analysis (ICCCBDA 2016) • IEEE International Conference on Information Reuse and Integration • The INNS Big Data conference • IEEE International Conference on Big Data and Cloud Computing
Indicative list of journals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big Data Research • Journal of Big Data • International Journal of Big Data Intelligence • Big Data and Information Analytics
Liaisons/Participation of Standardisation Committees	Schema.org community Group
Liaisons/Participation to related Industry Communities/Associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big Data Europe Community Group (W3C) • W3C KISS Community Group • Linked Building Data Community Group

Table 6 NTUA individual dissemination plan

FABLAB ROMANIA	
Description	FABLAB ROMANIA will disseminate the results of ToyLabs Project, within the organisation’s contacts, collaborators, numerous periodical workshops and events. FABLAB ROMANIA will also promote new collaboration in programs of science and technology dissemination.
Target audiences	The target audience will be set based on every type of toy, depending on the age groups relevant for the project.
Expected Impact of	The number of presentations and search groups will be set based

Activities	on the number of pilot case iterations necessary. E.g.: if the estimated number of iterations is 5, then we expect to have one presentation for each iteration.
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Table 7 FABLAB ROMANIA individual dissemination plan

START SMART SRL	
Description	<p>StartSmart will disseminate the results of ToyLabs Project, within Fab Lab digital fabrication and computation.</p> <p>StartSmart will disseminate the matured experience in term of developed methodology, technical invention and implemented prototyping solutions.</p> <p>The dissemination will be enabled in the Fab Lab Lecce. This Fab Lab will disseminate the ToyLabs project's outputs within the numerous periodical workshops and events. StartSmart will also help to disseminate the results of ToyLabs Project within its network and the promotion of new collaboration in programs of science and technology dissemination.</p>
Target audiences	European SME operating in Toy sector, scientific community and professional societies, European FabLab Community
Expected impact of activities	<p>The expected impact of Activities can be measured through the following outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information package like usage metrics on materials published (video tutorials, documentations) FabLab Project Community (Number of participants to "ToyLabs Call", Users Traction per month)
Indicative list of events, academic conferences, industry fairs	<p>StartSmart will publish papers on the project results, and will present the project at European and national conferences, conventions and exhibitions, both 3DP and FabLab innovations ones and those more oriented to Toy Industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The International FabLab Association (http://empty-ice-3260.herokuapp.com/) http://www.fabfoundation.org/ International Technology Management Conference (http://www.ice-conference.org/) Design Conference (http://www.designconference.org/)
Indicative list of journals	<p>Creativity and Innovation Management (http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(ISSN)1467-8691)</p> <p>Creativity Research Journal (http://www.tandfonline.com/toc/hcrj20/current)</p>

Table 8 START SMART SRL individual dissemination plan

V-CUBES	
Description	<p>CUBES will disseminate and communicate the ToyLabs concept, methodological approach and developments via the following indicative channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The organisation’s website; • The organisation’s social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn); • Various events and/or workshops that V-CUBES representatives participate.
Target Audiences	<p>Amongst the target audiences the following can be reported:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toy and other relevant manufacturers; • Distributors; • Customer base.

Table 9 V-CUBES individual dissemination plan

JUEMA	
Description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Press releases. Information about the participation in the project and the developments of the latter diffused between our clients and final consumers. 2. Participation in industry oriented Fairs. The company participates directly in 2 international fairs as : Nuremberg Toy Fair (January-Febr) and Madrid Gift Fair (in Jan. and in Sept.) as well as not direct participation in local toy fairs trough out the world with the help of our clients.
Target audiences	Industry experts, general public
Expected impact of activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 press releases/articles at specialized journal/newsletter • 3 Industrial Fair Participations
Liaisons/Participation to related Industry Communities Associations	INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA S.L. belongs to the Spanish Association of Toy Manufacturers and is an associated to AIJU that permits to improve our both commercial and internal manufacturing activities.

Table 10 JUEMA individual dissemination plan

